

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	2. Coiling	3. Plate Building
	4. Core Moulding	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	6. Other
B. TURNTABLE	?	C. WHEELMADE	?
E. CASTING			

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY			
GENERAL:	Coarse	← Medium X	Fine
1. Pebble	2. Granule	3. Very Coarse	4. Coarse
5. Medium	6. Fine	7. Very Fine	8. Silt
B. COMPOSITION	Type of Clay: Nile Alluvial		
TEMPER (General):	Heavy X	Medium	Light
1. Material	SAND (heavy)	Chaff, fiber	
2. Particle Size	to 1mm.	heavy but fine	
C. FRACTURE COLOR	General Description		Munsell
	DARK Grey to Dark brown at walls		
D. HARDNESS	MEDIUM	E. POROSITY	
F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH	G. PERMEABILITY		

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT			
1. Untreated	2. Wheel Finish	?	a. ribbing b. scrapped or shaved
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed	?	b. polished by burnishing c. polished by rubbing
	d. scrapped		e. scratched or combed X f. other
4. Coating	a. wash	b. slip	c. glaze
	Orangish wash, shows more interior wall, few traces on exterior when burnt away		
B. SURFACE TEXTURE	Exterior: Smooth; Interior: Grainy		
C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE	Exterior: Scratch (or comb) marks toward lower part - horizontal. Very faint fine horizontal striations show to upper part. Interior: Pronounced undulations, striations horizontal.		
D. LUSTER	1. Matte X	2. Low	3. Medium 4. High
E. SURFACE COLOR	General Description		Munsell CEC
	Original wash: Orange		Original wash: F9-69

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE			
1. Incised	2. Impressed	3. Gouged	4. Pinched
5. Modelled	6. Moulded	7. Painted	8. Inlaid

NOTE: WEAR AT FRACTURE may indicate reuse of sherd after breakage. Carbon on salt crystal growth at fracture may indicate burning after breakage of original vessel. On other hand, salt crystals could have pushed carbon out during their growth.